

Using flexible controller validation methods to advance the endorsement practices in a Remote Tower Centre - A first survey

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Abstract— In the 2010s, remote tower technology revolutionised the management and control of traffic at small and medium-sized aerodromes, providing high-quality service at low costs. Since then, the number of remotely controlled airports has continuously increased worldwide. These airports' remote aerodrome control units are increasingly concentrated in remote tower centres, where the same staff provides air traffic control services to multiple airports, similar to how area control centres manage different sectors. One constraint that currently prevents the full exploitation of the advantages offered by remote tower centres are the existing regulations regarding controller licensing, training, and endorsements. Specifically, the obligation to perform on-the-job training for each aerodrome, leading to a unit endorsement for each aerodrome as is done for conventional towers, results in high training costs and long training times. The new SESAR project IFAV3 investigates new ways to reduce training time and effort using procedural means or technical assistance tools. The ultimate goal is to enable air traffic controllers to obtain and maintain more unit endorsements in parallel than is currently possible and at reasonable costs. A part of the project is dedicated to applying this concept to a remote tower centre. In this framework, a first survey was conducted in the early summer of 2024 to gather initial feedback and inputs from operational experts regarding the feasibility and applicability of the concept in a remote tower centre and identify any existing concerns. 38 air traffic controllers from across Europe responded to the survey. Apart from some safety concerns, participants shared their views and expectations regarding operational efficiency, cost efficiency, environmental impact, workload changes, situational awareness, job satisfaction, and trust. This paper provides more information about the survey's background, describes the methodology used, and presents detailed results. It concludes with a thorough discussion and presentation of the main findings and conclusions.

Keywords— *IFAV, increased flexibility, ATCO deployment, flexible rostering, generic controller validations, unit endorsement*

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the newest developments that will significantly change how Air Traffic Controllers (ATCOs) work is the introduction of Remote Tower Control. High-resolution cameras mounted on one or more masts replace the outside view of the aerodrome control tower, and the live images are transmitted to a remote Controller Working Position (CWP) and displayed there on large window-like screens. Developed in the 2000s, Remote Tower Technology promises several advantages over a traditional tower building at an airport [1][2][3]:

- The construction and maintenance costs are much lower for camera masts than for a complete tower building.
- Due to the digitalisation of the outside view, the remote tower technology offers numerous options for enhancements and/or augmentations, such as overlays, aircraft labels, head-up displays, infrared views, automatic visual tracking, or extreme zoom, which is not possible with handheld binoculars.
- As long distances between the camera mast and the CWP are now possible, the remote tower technology offers options for a more flexible and cost-efficient aerodrome control service provision, for example, to more aerodromes with very low traffic and/or which would require only a temporary service provision.

Although there might still be some reservations about providing remote tower service, the advantages of this technology are widely recognised. For this reason, the number of remotely controlled airports continuously increases, and this trend can be expected to intensify further.

Due to the flexibility offered by this new technology, an increasing number of remotely controlled airports are served from Remote Tower Centres (RTCs), where the same ATCO staff uses standardised controller working positions in a control room to provide aerodrome control service for various aerodromes. An RTC can be seen as equivalent to an Area Control Centre (ACC), in which the same ATCO staff provides approach and area control service for several air traffic control (ATC) sectors, using standardised CWPs [1][2][3].

However, since the first RTCs were established only a few years ago, their implementation and development can still be considered ongoing. One example is that the applicable ATCO endorsement regulations remain the same as those for conventional towers. These regulations require a unit endorsement per aerodrome and, consequently, complete traditional on-the-job (OJT) training per aerodrome [4]. One of the main technical advantages an RTC offers is the possibility to easily and flexibly provide service to various aerodromes independent of their geographical location. The restriction set by traditional training and endorsement practices directly leads to a significant effort in time and costs that must be spent on on-the-job training for every ATCO at every airport controlled by the same RTC.

One solution to this situation could be applying methods and concepts investigated within the 'Increased Flexibility of ATCO Validations' (IFAV) research for upper-area control. This approach explores the possibility of a

more flexible ATCO deployment to sectors where similar challenges and constraints must be solved. In the following sections, we will refer to this as the IFAV3 concept.

A. Background

The IFAV research started in 2016 in the frame of the SESAR programme with the project PJ.10-06, which investigated so-called non-geographical controller validations. The initial concept was to replace sector-based endorsements with a new type of endorsement, which can, for example, be sector-type-based or system-based, similar to type ratings for pilots.

The PJ.10-06 project was followed by two other SESAR projects, PJ.10-73 IFAV and PJ.33. In these projects, the ultimate goal was less to remove the geographical reference of unit endorsements to sectors, and more to use technical or procedural means or a combination of them, to reduce the need to train geographical features and local procedures of a sector. The focus was mainly on area control service for aircraft in the en-route phase of flight. Both projects ended in June 2023 [6].

Within the new IFAV3 project, a SESAR project that started in July 2023, this research is continued in two parts, called 'Solutions' in the SESAR language. Within Solution 1, the IFAV concept is further matured to a pre-implementation state for the upper airspace, covering four strategies for a more flexible ATCO deployment to sectors. At the same time, IFAV3 Solution 1 is seen as a mandatory enabler for the Virtual Centre Concept [8].

IFAV3 Solution 2 aims to transfer the IFAV know-how and methods to the environment of an RTC for the first time, where very similar challenges compared to those in an ACC are to be solved. Nevertheless, significant differences between both working environments make it necessary to revise and adapt the IFAV concepts to the Tower business, investigate different enablers, and start again with a feasibility study.

Within IFAV3 Solution 2, a review of already addressed IFAV procedures, strategies, and means for the upper airspace is conducted, followed by an applicability/gap analysis for RTCs. Several procedural and technical means are designed according to the IFAV idea for this new environment, and finally, a validation exercise is planned as a workshop with operational experts in the second half of 2025 [9].

As preparation and first input for tool development on the one hand, but also for setting up the validation plan on the other hand, a first survey was developed and administered in June 2024. In this survey, several initial ideas for possible enablers that might support the implementation of the IFAV idea are investigated:

- **Procedural enablers:** Simplification and standardisation of local aerodrome procedures; aerodrome clustering;
- **Technical enablers:** Pre-Shift Briefing/Learning Tools, Real-Time Learning Tools, Post-Shift Learning Tools, (Adaptive) Information Display Tools, Advisory Tools, Single Task Automation.

As the development is still in progress, the enablers mentioned above represent the initial categories to be utilised. Throughout the development process, these enablers will be further refined and characterised.

The following sections of this paper discuss more details about this survey's methodology and results.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Survey administration

The survey, conducted via Google Forms from June to July 2024, was accessible on laptops, tablets, or smartphones. Recruitment emails were sent to air navigation service providers and towers across Europe, inviting ATCOs to participate in the SESAR 3 JU project's IFAV3 study, focusing on RTC operations. The email provided a project overview and a survey link and assured voluntary and anonymous participation. Upon accessing the survey, participants reviewed the objectives and consent form, confirming they were at least 18 and agreed to participate. Submission implied consent for anonymised data usage and compliance with the IFAV3 Privacy Policy. Participants were then provided detailed information about the IFAV3 project and survey instructions, emphasising responses based on their knowledge and experience.

B. Survey design and development

The survey comprised 23 questions covering key issues around the IFAV3 concept applied in a Remote Tower environment and its impact on operations.

1. **Demographic data and familiarity with the concept of the Remote-Control Tower:** The survey began by collecting demographic data, including participants' ages. It then explored participants' backgrounds as ATCOs,

focusing on their current roles, total years of ATCO experience, and duration in their current positions. The survey then assessed participants' familiarity with Remote Tower operations. Participants were asked about their awareness of the concept and whether they had prior experience working in a Remote Tower environment. Participants were also asked how many different aerodromes they had managed throughout their careers to provide initial insight into the experience level regarding managing multiple aerodromes.

2. IFAV3 concept definition: This section gathered feedback on several key aspects by asking the participants about I. The possibility of grouping multiple aerodromes under unit endorsement for ATCOs; II. The optimal number of clustered aerodromes an ATCO can effectively manage; III. The impact of IFAV3 on training duration compared to traditional per-aerodrome training. IV. The possibility of reducing Pre-OJT and OJT phases using the IFAV3 solution; V. Whether the proposed procedural and technical enablers of IFAV3 would sufficiently support reduced Pre-OJT and OJT time and effort for maintaining proficiency.

3. Expected Impact of the IFAV3 solution: This section gathered ATCOs' perspectives on the potential impact of the IFAV3 solution in terms of Human Performance, Safety, Cost Efficiency, Operational Efficiency, and Environment. ATCOs evaluated:

a. Human Performance: The influence of IFAV3 on workload, trust, situation awareness, job satisfaction, and the risk of skill fading, using a 5-point scale (1 = Significant Reduction to 5 = Significant Increase).

b. Safety: The ability to manage multiple airfields under a single endorsement and the impact of flexible deployment on safety, rated from 1 (Totally Disagree) to 5 (Totally Agree). They also provided brief written responses on potential safety-related concerns.

c. Cost Efficiency, Operational Efficiency, and Environment: The impact on cost efficiency, operational efficiency, and environmental effects, rated from 1 (Significant Negative Impact) to 5 (Significant Positive Impact), with additional brief written responses to explain their ratings.

C. Participants

Thirty-eight subject matter experts (SMEs), all qualified ATCOs, participated in this research. Among them, 52.6% were Conventional Tower Controllers (CTCs) aged between 32-41 (Mean (M) =2,40; Standard Deviation (SD) =1,05) and with 10-14 years of experience (M=2,90; SD=1,41); 15.8% were Remote Tower Controllers (RTCOs) aged between 30-39 (M=2,33; SD=1,03) and with 11-15 years of experience (M=3,00; SD=1,68); and the remaining 31.6% held other roles, including Area Controllers (ACs), former ATCOs, and Approach / Tower ATCO trainers. This last group, referred to as the Other group, was aged between 45-54 (M=3.50; SD=1,00) and had 16-20 years of experience (M=4,25; SD=1,21). Considering the responses from the Other group, which includes controllers who may not be directly familiar with the concept of remote tower operations, provides a broader perspective on the applicability of the IFAV3 Solution 2 concept. As potential future users of this concept, their input offers valuable insights derived from an external point of view, which could be instrumental in evaluating the generalisability and adaptability of the proposed solution.

D. Data collection and analyses

The analyses included responses from all participants and were conducted using SPSS version 29 [10]. Responses to open-ended questions were summarised in concise sentences and analysed separately. This approach helped highlight the primary concerns and benefits spontaneously reported by ATCOs regarding the IFAV3 concept and validate the findings from close-ended questions.

The analyses explored participants' perspectives on the IFAV3 concept and its potential operational impact. Descriptive statistics accompanied by bar charts were run for this purpose. Additionally, the study aimed to assess whether significant differences existed among participants categorized by role, age, and experience regarding their views on the concept and its operational implications.

To investigate potential differences in participants' responses concerning the IFAV3 concept, a CrossTab analysis using the Fisher-Freeman-Halton Test [11] was conducted. Participants were grouped according to their roles, ages, and years of experience.

Furthermore, to examine differences in participants' responses concerning the anticipated impact of the IFAV3 solution on operations, the Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric Test [12], followed by Post Hoc Tests, was performed to identify exactly which groups differed from each other. Once again, participants were categorised based on their roles, age, and years of experience. The use of non-parametric tests was due to substantial violations of the database's normality assumption.

III. RESULTS

A. Feedback on Concept Feasibility

Overall, most of the surveyed ATCOs (58%) consider the concept of clustering different aerodromes within the same unit endorsement feasible. This indicates general acceptance and optimism about the potential for operational efficiency and flexibility such clustering could offer.

The average response to how many aerodromes can be clustered together effectively was 2-3, reflecting a realistic and manageable scope for most ATCOs. This manageable scope ensures that ATCOs can maintain high situational awareness and control levels without becoming overwhelmed, balancing the efficiency benefits with operational safety.

Notably, ATCOs with prior experience in RTCs are more inclined to find the concept feasible, with 83.3% affirming the possibility of clustering different aerodromes within the same unit endorsement (Figure 1) and condensing or modifying the Pre OJT/OJT training (Figure 2).

Fig. 1. Responses concerning the possibility of clustering aerodromes in the same unit endorsement (Light Grey: Remote Tower Controller; White: Conventional Tower Controller; Dark Grey: Other Group)

Fig. 2. Responses concerning the possibility of condensing/modifying Pre- OJT / OJT phases

The Fisher-Freeman-Halton Test [11] was used to examine the association between the role variables and the suitability of the proposed technical and procedural enablers to allow a reduced Pre OJT/OJT time and effort for endorsement and maintenance. The results show a significant association at the 5% significance level between role and the suitability of the enablers to allow a reduced Pre OJT time and effort for endorsement ($\chi^2 = 5.60$, $p = 0.05$). In particular, those participants in RTC roles showed a higher inclination (83%) to use the enablers to reduce the Pre OJT time and effort for endorsement compared to Conventional Tower Controllers (CTC) and the Other groups (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Responses concerning the use of enablers

Feedback from the ATCOs highlights the need for further development of the enablers to reduce OJT times and efforts and ongoing maintenance training. Specifically, 66% find the enablers need more to reduce OJT times and efforts, and 55% view them as inadequate for continuing maintenance training. This feedback indicates a gap that needs to be addressed to ensure the concept's successful implementation. Additionally, only the categories of enablers were given to them in the survey introduction, not the detailed enablers, which may have influenced the response.

Furthermore, there is a concern that reliance on these enablers could lead to skill fading among ATCOs, with 76% expressing this concern. This suggests developing countermeasures or mitigation strategies to ensure long-term proficiency is unaffected. A key aspect of the concept's feasibility is the potential for standardisation. The survey responses suggest that aligning procedures across multiple remotely controlled aerodromes is achievable and could serve as a crucial enabler for the concept, with 61% of ATCOs supporting this idea. Standardisation is seen as a pathway to minimise procedural differences between aerodromes, simplifying the operational environment for ATCOs and resulting in lower training requirements. Possible solutions include incorporating extra simulator hours without tools to maintain skill levels. Additionally, further research and development are required to enhance the procedural and technical enablers to a level where they can effectively reduce training and maintenance efforts without compromising the quality and safety of air traffic control operations.

B. Impact on Safety, Cost Efficiency, Operational Efficiency, Environment

31.6% of ATCOs indicated uncertainty about whether cluster-endorsed ATCOs can safely and efficiently handle the same aerodromes under the IFAV3 solution. Additionally, a significant proportion (34.2%) perceived a reduction in safety levels for ATCOs flexibly deployed to different aerodromes with the IFAV3 solution compared to traditional training and endorsement methods. This suggests that, with the information provided to air traffic controllers still in its preliminary stages, the IFAV3 approach may introduce concerns about maintaining consistent safety standards.

The Kruskal-Wallis test [12] revealed significant differences between roles regarding perceptions of whether cluster-endorsed ATCOs can handle the same aerodromes safely and efficiently ($H(2) = 8.06, p < .005$). Post-hoc analysis indicated that the RTCO group perceived this capability more positively compared to the Conventional Tower group ($p = .03$) and the Other group ($p = .02$), as highlighted in Figure 4:

Fig. 4. Results of the Kruskal-Wallis-Test (Multiple aerodromes can be handled safely with the concept 1=totally disagree, 5=totally agree)

Controllers' feedback reports that the most critical safety-related events foreseen include the loss of situational awareness, mixing up procedures and traffic patterns, cognitive limitations, confusion regarding local

geography, handling emergencies differently at various aerodromes, increased reliance on technical systems, mixing up runway instructions, increased stress and fatigue, and coordination errors during simultaneous safety events at multiple aerodromes.

At the time of this paper, only the categories of enablers have been provided without detailing the specific tools. Further elaboration on these tools is essential to develop systems that mitigate the criticalities above.

Regarding cost efficiency, 87% of respondents foresee no impact from the IFAV3 solution (Figure 5). While potential operational cost reductions due to enhanced flexibility and reduced staffing are anticipated, substantial initial investments in technology, ongoing maintenance expenses, and continuous training requirements could negate these savings.

Fig. 5. Expected impact on Cost Efficiency

Operational efficiency is expected to decrease slightly, according to 86% of respondents, likely due to increased operational complexity, diminished local knowledge, and the necessity for synchronised operations across multiple airports, potentially leading to delays and reduced adaptability due to standardised procedures (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Expected impact on Operational Efficiency

Concerning environmental impact, the plurality of ATCOs (47%) anticipate no significant change in fuel efficiency, noise levels, or local air quality under IFAV3 compared to traditional methods, with flights and operations expected to remain largely unchanged (Figure 7).

Fig. 7. Expected impact on the Environment

C. Impact on Human Factors

The study's analysis integrated results from both quantitative and qualitative analyses to ensure an accurate interpretation of the findings.

Participants' perceptions of the IFAV3 new concept suggested a potential moderate increase in workload, as reported by 60% of respondents (Figure 8). A crosstab analysis revealed that 67% of RTCO and other groups

reported a perception of a moderate increase in workload compared to 55% of CTC participants. This potential workload elevation, highlighted in the qualitative responses, was primarily attributed to the need for ATCOs to familiarise themselves with new enablers and interfaces. This initial learning curve impacted situational awareness (SA), too, due to increased cognitive load, with 50% of participants reporting a moderate reduction in SA (Figure 9). The Kruskal-Wallis Test [12] reported no significant differences between roles, ages, or experience levels regarding workload and situational awareness.

Fig. 8. Expected impact on ATCO Workload

Fig. 9. Expected impact on ATCO Situational Awareness

However, this adaptation will enhance workload management and situational awareness over time. These findings were further supported by results indicating a moderate increase in job satisfaction among ATCOs (55%), suggesting that the new tools may enhance work quality. Additionally, the level of trust remained unchanged, with 34.5% of ATCOs expressing no changes in their confidence (Figure 11).

Regarding job satisfaction, the plurality of ATCOs (26.3%) reported no changes or a moderate increase (Figure 10).

Fig. 10. Expected impact on ATCO Job Satisfaction

Fig. 11. Expected impact on ATCO Trust

The Kruskal-Wallis Test [12] revealed no significant differences among age, experience, role, workload levels, situational awareness, trust, and job satisfaction. This consistency across demographic groups reinforces the overall findings and supports the potential for broader applicability of the IFAV3 concept.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

According to the qualitative feedback gained from the survey, participants perceive the overall concept as feasible. They affirm the possibility of shortening the OJT duration and reducing the effort for endorsement maintenance for several aerodromes in an RTC environment. Therefore, the project ambitions can be considered achievable.

Standardisation across remote tower-controlled airports is seen as a suitable enabler to reach this goal and presents a promising area for further exploration as a potential mitigation strategy. However, there are general doubts about whether the technical and procedural enablers described in the survey are sufficient. This is understandable, given that the research on these IFAV enablers for an RTC environment started in 2023 and still has a low maturity level.

Nevertheless, participants say the possibility of shortening OJT and reducing endorsement maintenance efforts is limited. Even with tools and enablers, ATCOs need adequate time for proper training, and reducing the training time at a specific airport beyond that limit introduces safety risks.

The survey also investigated the possibility of clustering several remotely controlled airports in a cluster endorsement. The survey revealed no clear consensus on the feasibility and safety of a cluster endorsement. However, participants with experience in an RTC environment are more optimistic about cluster endorsements, while conventional tower participants are more pessimistic.

A. Main Findings and Conclusions

Regarding the assessed performance areas, the following main findings can be highlighted and summarised, and the following conclusions can be drawn:

- **Safety:** The participants reported several safety concerns. These concerns mainly refer to a significant reduction in OJT duration and rotating ATCOs over several different aerodromes in an RTC, especially when combined in a cluster endorsement.
- **Workload:** A moderate increase in ATCO workload is expected when using the IFAV concept in an RTC. This increase can be caused by reduced training time, which results in lower work routine and, consequently, a higher perceived workload. However, it must be investigated if this workload increase is acceptable, as typical remote tower airports usually have a low traffic volume.
- **Trust:** No changes were reported, and no impacts are expected.
- **Situation Awareness and Operational Efficiency:** Participants expect a negative impact. This can be explained by doubts about whether the technical and procedural enablers are sufficient and the increased reliance on these enablers instead of a full traditional OJT. With this in mind, the feedback can be understood as an initial assessment of the impact when OJT duration is reduced without proper compensation.
- **Job Satisfaction:** At least no change, possibly an increase, is expected. This can be due to the greater variety of work when ATCOs are deployed to different airports according to the IFAV concept without the need for numerous months or years of OJT.
- **Cost Efficiency:** The results of the survey are contradictory here. On the one hand, participants generally expected no overall impact on cost efficiency, neither positive nor negative. On the other hand, they reported potential for long-term cost savings and reduced training costs. Answers point towards the expectation that investment costs compensate for cost savings. However, the investment costs of IFAV procedures and tools implementation may have been mixed up with the investment costs of RTC implementation in this survey. Therefore, an increase in cost efficiency can still be expected when implementing the IFAV concept in an RTC.
- **Environment:** The participants generally expect no positive or negative impact. Nevertheless, this has to be closely monitored for further research, as less training can reduce operational efficiency, leading to more delays and emissions.

B. Limitations of the Survey

This study was conducted to gather initial feedback and input from operational experts on the feasibility, applicability, and existing concerns related to the IFAV3 concept. In this regard, the discussed results should be analysed considering certain limitations in the study's conduct, particularly those related to the survey.

This survey's relatively small sample size may limit its representativeness of the larger Air Traffic Controllers (ATCOs)

population. Additionally, the study's sample is unbalanced, comprising 20 Conventional ATCOs, 12 ATCOs belonging to the Other Group category, and 6 Remote Towers ATCOs, further reducing the latter group's representativeness.

The survey was also conducted among various ATCO roles to compare perceptions and gather comprehensive feedback. However, this approach may result in unbalanced responses, as ATCOs with prior experience or more excellent knowledge of the Remote Tower concept might provide more informed and nuanced answers than other groups.

Finally, the questionnaire reflects the project's developmental stage, as, at the time of writing this paper, only the categories of enablers were provided rather than the actual enablers. Consequently, the responses may be biased, reflecting the immaturity of the concept at this stage.

C. Recommended Improvements and Outlook

Several key improvements and future directions are recommended to advance the IFAV3 concept. Continued development of technical and procedural enablers is crucial, with standardisation emerging as a promising approach that could significantly enhance the concept's feasibility and applicability. Addressing skill fading among Air Traffic Controllers (ATCOs) is imperative to maintain and improve proficiency through increased simulator hours.

Looking ahead, within the IFAV3 project, the development of enablers will continue throughout 2025, with plans for a series of validation exercises involving expert workshops. A follow-up project is anticipated for 2026 and beyond to build on the insights gained and address any remaining challenges. With these initiatives, operational implementation of the IFAV3 concept is expected to be feasible within the coming years, making a more effective and standardised approach to remote tower operations possible.

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